

An Analytical Study of Credit Risk Management and Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in India : A CAMEL Model Approach

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Abstract : *This paper explores and analyses the financial performance and credit risk management practices of selected private sector and public sector banks in India. The paper encompasses the study six Indian commercial banks including three from each public sector and private sector. The data for the period of 15 years, commencing from accounting year 2007-08 to 2021-2022 has been taken into consideration. The dependent variable for the study is ROE and the CAMEL components are the independent variables. A standard multiple regression model has been applied for assessing the relationship between the CAMEL model parameters and the performance indicator (ROE) of the banks since there are several independent variables in the study. The overall performance ranking of selected banks during the study period reveals that the HDFC Bank is ranked first in the overall financial performance followed by Axis Bank while Punjab National Bank sits on the last rank. It is evident from the data analysis that the capital adequacy, asset quality and earning capacity has a statistically significant effect on the performance (ROE) of the selected banks for the period under study.*

Keywords : CAMEL Model, ROE, Credit Risk Management, Financial Performance, Commercial Banks.

1. Introduction

Banks have by far been one of the most significant and oldest institutions fuelling the development of the Indian economy (Rostami, 2015). Banks have been rendering unmatched financial assistance to most of the businesses. The activities of the bank lie around accepting deposits and channelizing those deposits into loans and advances and investments in the capital market. The Indian banking

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industry has witnessed magnanimous growth and development in the last two decades over innovation and technology. Like any other business activity, banks require funds to carry out their business operations (Balasundaram, 2008). This involves management of funds and ensuring its effective channelization to avoid any crunch. The banks while carrying out their operations are exposed to multiple risks at various facets. These risks involve market risk, credit risk, liquidity risk and operational risk (Roy, Nanda, & Goswami, 2020). It becomes imperative for a bank to effectively manage the risks it is exposed to so that financial efficiency can be maintained. This paper explores and analyses the financial performance and credit risk management practices of selected public sector and private sector banks in India. The asset quality of the banks has continually been tapered down, which makes it important to measure and analyse the performance of Indian banks.

1.1. Credit Risk Management

Lending credit forms one of the focal activities of the banks in which banks form an agreement with the lender to grant something of value today with the promise of receiving the same value along with some predetermined rate of interest at a future date. Credit lending activities of the bank give birth to credit risk. Credit risk refers to the probability of loss that will be incurred by the bank if the borrower fails to repay the debt and become insolvent. Credit risk management is a tool which helps the banks to reduce credit risk related losses by giving an understanding of maintaining adequate capital and credit loss reserves at every point of time (Selvaraj & Devi, 2022). Credit creation is the primary income generating activity of the banks and involves taking sizable credit related risks.

1.2. CAMEL Model

CAMEL is a global rating system employed by regulatory banking authorities to evaluate financial institutions based on the five factors denoted by its acronym. The Federal Financial Institutions Examinations Council (FFIEC) of the United States of America first embraced the CAMEL model of the Uniform Financial Institutions Rating System (UFIRS) on November 13, 1979. In an effort to determine a bank's overall financial status, the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC) later updated the UFIRS to include a sixth indicator (Sensitivity) in 1997 (Selvaraj & Devi, 2022). CAMEL is an abbreviation that represents the following five critical factors in assessing financial institutions: "Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Management, Earnings, and Liquidity."

In this study, five set of ratios has been applied according to CAMEL model and are summarised in a relative model of that category. The following group of ratios are mentioned as under:

1.2.1. Capital Adequacy

The level of capital adequacy measures the degree to which an organisation complies with rules regarding the required minimum capital reserve. The grade is determined by regulators by considering the capital status of the financial institution both now and in the past. The following indicators have been considered for the study:

Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) : The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), also referred to as the Capital to Risk (Weighted) Assets Ratio (CRAR), is a measure that assesses a bank's capital relative to the level of risk it holds. Central banks and banking regulators determine this ratio to mitigate the risk of commercial banks overleveraging themselves and potentially facing insolvency. CAR quantifies the proportion of a bank's capital compared to its risk-weighted assets and current liabilities.

$$\text{CAR} = \frac{\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital}}{\text{Risk weighted Assets}} \quad (1)$$

Equity multiplier ratio : The equity multiplier indicates a risk indicator that calculates the percentage of a company's assets that are funded by equity rather than debt. The equity multiplier is computed by dividing the entire asset value of a firm by the total equity held in the company's shares.

$$\text{Equity Multiplier} = \frac{\text{Total Assets}}{\text{Shareholder's Equity}} \quad (2)$$

1.2.2. Asset Quality

This classification rates the value of a bank's assets. Asset quality is crucial because high-risk assets might see rapid decline in their value. It addresses the loan's quality, which indicates the institution's profits. When evaluating asset quality, banks must rank the potential investment risks. The following ratios have been considered for the study:

Net NPA ratio : NPA is a loan or advance that becomes overdue for 90 days or more. The amount of GNPA left after deducting unpaid and doubtful debts is called net NPA (Vinayak Hagargi, 2023).

$$\text{Net NPA} = \text{Gross NPA} - \text{Provisions} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Net NPA Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net NPA}}{\text{Net Advances}} \quad (4)$$

Return on assets (ROA) : ROA is the measure of profit that can be earned from a bank's assets. The return on assets ratio or ROA measures how efficiently a bank can manage its assets to produce profits during a period (My Accounting Course, 2023).

$$\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (5)$$

1.2.3. Management

The ability of an institution's management team to recognise and respond to financial crisis is determined by management competency. This classification is based on the effectiveness of a bank's internal controls, financial performance, and business strategy. The following ratios have been considered for the study:

Cost to income ratio : The cost to income ratio, calculates operating expenses as a share of operating income. The ratio should be as low as feasible, but not so low that it compromises customer service. The banks anticipate, lowering their cost-to-income ratio as their business expands in order to achieve the economies to scale. It is a measure of operating efficiency of a bank and signifies the cost as a proportion of its income.

$$\text{CIR} = \frac{\text{Operating Expense}}{\text{Operating Income}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Operating expense to total asset ratio : The ability to observe changes in operating costs in relation to asset changes makes the operating cost to asset ratio an essential efficiency measure. It also serves as a gauge of the business mix of the bank. In order to evaluate the efficiency of the banks, it may be compared across time and with other banks (Stock Edge, 2019).

$$\text{Operating Expense to Asset Ratio} = \frac{\text{Operating Expense}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (7)$$

1.2.4. Earnings

Earnings are an excellent tool for assessing an institution's long-term sustainability. A bank requires a reasonable return in order to expand its business and keep up its competitiveness. The core earnings are the most significant when evaluating earnings of the banks. The core earnings of an institution are its long-term, steady earnings, which are impacted by the cost of one-time items. The following ratios have been considered for the study:

Net interest margin (NIM) : A financial firm's net interest income is measured using the term net interest margin. It is generated by credit products like loans and mortgages and the interest that is charged to those who have savings accounts and deposit certificates. (CDs). The NIM, which is an indicator of profitability, expressed as a percentage, predicts the likelihood that a bank or investment business will be successful over the long term (Annapoorna, 2023). The total interest received left with the bank after making interest payments as a proportion of interest yielding assets of the bank.

$$\text{NIM} = \frac{(\text{Interest Received} - \text{Interest Paid})}{\text{Average Earning Assets}} \quad (8)$$

Operating profit to total asset ratio (OP/TA) : Operating profit to total asset ratio is the proportion of the total asset base of the banks. It is a profitability ratio that assesses how well a bank utilizes its assets to produce net income. It shows a bank's profitability in relation to its total assets. A high ratio indicates that a bank's primary business is its only source of income, revealing the management's ability to generate profits. It shows that a bank is utilising its assets more efficiently when its earnings are higher in relation to its assets (M & Rajan.K., 2016).

$$\text{Operating Profit to Total Assets Ration} = \frac{\text{Operating Profit}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (9)$$

1.2.5. Liquidity

Liquidity is crucial for banks since it can prevent bank failures if there is enough liquid capital. This CAMEL category investigates interest rate risk and liquidity risk. Earnings from the capital markets business section of a bank are influenced by interest rates. The value of the institution's investment and loan portfolio will fluctuate if there is a significant exposure to interest rate risk. Liquidity risk

is the possibility of not being able to fulfil current or future cash flow requirements without interfering with regular business operations (CFI Team, 2022). The following ratios have been considered for the study.

CASA ratio : The CASA ratio reveals the percentage of current and savings accounts in a bank's total deposits. A higher ratio indicates cheaper cost of funds since a greater proportion of a bank's total deposits are in current and savings accounts. Therefore, the cost of handling the money will be cheaper, the bigger the deposits are in each of these accounts (StockEdge, 2018).

$$\text{CASA Ratio} = \frac{(\text{Current Deposit} + \text{Savings Deposits})}{\text{Total Deposits}} \quad (10)$$

Loan to deposit ratio (LDR) : The loan-to-deposit ratio measures a bank's total loans to its total deposits for the same time period. LDR is expressed as a percentage and is employed to figure out the liquidity status of a bank. The bank may not have adequate liquidity to meet any unanticipated funding needs if the ratio is too high. If the ratio is too low, on the other hand, the bank could not be making as much money as it might (Murphy, 2020).

$$\text{LDR} = \frac{\text{Total Loan}}{\text{Total Deposits}} \quad (11)$$

1.2.6. Return on equity (ROE)

Return on equity, often known as ROE, is a metric used to assess a bank's performance over a specific time period. The bank's ability to generate returns on the investments it received from its shareholders is measured by its return on equity. As a result, before investing their money in a financial institution, potential investors frequently take the ROE into consideration. A bank is better at turning its equity funding into profits, if the ROE is higher (Groww, 2022).

$$\text{ROE} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Shareholder's Equity}} \quad (12)$$

2. Review of Literature

Chhetri (2021) put forward that the impact of non-performing loans (NPLR) on financial performance is adverse and statistically significant. (ROA). Financial performance is negatively impacted by capital adequacy ratio and bank size;

however, this influence is statistically insignificant. The association between credit to deposit (CDR) and financial success is favourable but not very substantial. The study also found a substantial and positive association between the management quality ratio (MQR) and the financial performance (ROA) of Nepal's commercial banks. In order to protect their assets to the greatest extent possible, Nepalese commercial banks are advised to practise scientific credit risk management, enhance the effectiveness of their credit analysis, and manage their loans more effectively. This will help to reduce the high incidence of non-performing loans and their detrimental effects on financial performance.

Boateng & Nagaraju, (2020) had conducted a study to examine the productivity levels of 12 PSBs in India. According to the findings of the ANOVA analysis on the parameters relating to management efficiency, there were different levels of management efficiency across the banks. Three of the four variables used in the study—PPE, BPE, and salaries to costs ratio—were statistically significant at the .05 level of significance, according to the findings of an ANOVA on employee efficiency characteristics. As a result, it is advised that public sector banks in India raise employee and management productivity at each of their individual institutions in order to boost output and, by extension, profitability.

Boateng (2019) has applied the CAMELS rating model to evaluate the performance of Ghanaian banks. Following an analysis of the ratios derived from the financial statements of the chosen banks, it was discovered that earnings was the most significant factor influencing the performance of Ghanaian banks. A change in earnings as a percentage will result in a staggering 82.5% improvement in bank performance as determined by ROE. Liquidity, asset quality, managerial effectiveness, and capital sufficiency were all shown to have a similar substantial impact on the performance of Ghanaian banks.

According to Rauf (2016), the banking industry is one of the most competitive industries in the current economic climate. It has been suggested that CD Bank and GH Bank have better liquidity ratios than other banks, indicating that these banks have a greater ability to meet their customers' obligations. Therefore, before choosing the best bank for their investment and other banking needs, the consumer should take into account interest rate, credibility, good will, and other facilities & perks.

Erol (2017) employed the CAMEL model to compare the performance of Islamic banks in Turkey to that of regular banks. The findings demonstrated that Islamic banks outperformed conventional banks in terms of profitability and asset management ratios, but lagged behind in terms of sensitivity to market risk criteria.

Majumder & Rahman (2016) adopted the CAMEL Model to assess the financial performance of 15 Bangladeshi banks. He came to the conclusion that there had been a substantial difference in the performance of the chosen banks using Composite Ranking, average, and ANOVA. The researcher recommended that banks must take the necessary action to fix these flaws.

3. Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the management of credit risk has become increasingly difficult for the Indian banking sector, including both banking and Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs) which led to the failure, liquidation, and consolidation of the nation's banks and NBFCs. As a result, the public is beginning to lose faith in the banking industry. In light of this situation, the current study has been designed to use the CAMEL model to figure out the link between credit risk management and the performance of Indian commercial banks.

4. Objectives of the Study

The study aims to achieve the following primary objectives:

- To assess the viability of the selected Indian banks from a financial standpoint.
- To assess the relationship between the parameters of CAMEL model and the performance of the selected banks.

5. Research Methodology

5.1. Research Design

The study relies solely on an empirical research methodology. The research that is based on empirical observation and measurement of occurrences as they are really experienced by the researcher is known as empirical research design.

5.2. Scope of the Study

The present study is restricted to six Indian commercial banks including three from each public sector and private sector. The data for the period of 15 years, commencing from accounting year 2007-08 to 2021-2022 has been taken into consideration.

5.3. Sample Profile

The random sampling technique has been used to select the sample banks. The sample size includes a total of six banks namely AXIS, HDFC, KOTAK Mahindra,

BOB, PNB and Union bank. A regression analysis of the parameters of CAMEL model has been performed, in order to clearly identify the institutional strengths and shortcomings of the selected banks in all the dimensions of financial and management capabilities.

5.4. Variables of the Study

The financial performance of the banks, as determined by the Return on Equity (ROE), was utilized as the dependent variable and the CAMEL model components represented the independent variables for the study.

5.5. Research Model

A standard multiple regression model has been applied for assessing the relationship between the CAMEL model parameters and the performance indicator (ROE) of the banks since there are several independent variables in the study. The following equation served as the research model for the study:

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1C + \beta_2A + \beta_3M + \beta_4E + \beta_5L + \varepsilon \quad (13)$$

Where, ROE = Return on Equity (performance indicator); C = Capital Adequacy; A = Asset Quality; M = Management Efficiency; E = Earning Capacity; L = Liquidity; β_0 = Intercept (constant term); ε = the error term; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ are the coefficients of the respective independent variables.

5.6. Sources of Data Collection

The research work relies on secondary data sources which have been compiled from the various annual reports, RBI bulletins, journals, websites, etc.

5.7. Statistical Tools and Analysis

Several statistical techniques, including mean, standard deviation, and others, were used to analyse the data. To investigate the relationship and ascertain the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variables, the linear regression approach has been applied. The study hypothesis has been put to the test, and the results have been validated, using the Independent Sample t-test and the ANOVA.

5.8. Hypothesis of the Study

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the CAMEL parameters and the performance indicator (ROE) of the selected banks.

5.9. Limitations of the Study

The study has a few limitations as it is based radically on secondary data. The data has been taken as at balance sheet date. The research work is time bound and the findings may differ for different set of banks as only certain criteria has been taken up.

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1. Overall Performance Ranking of Selected Banks during the Period 2008-2022

Bank	ROE	C	A	M	E	L	Average	Rank
HDFC	6	2	6	2	5	5	4.33	1
Axis Bank	4	3	5	3	4	4	3.83	2
Kotak Mahindra	5	1	4	1	6	6	3.83	2
BOB	3	5	3	6	2	2	3.50	4
Union Bank	2	6	2	5	1	1	2.83	5
PNB	1	4	1	4	3	3	2.67	6

Source: All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Table-1 presented above illustrates the comprehensive ranking of the financial performance of selected public sector and private sector banks spanning from 2008 to 2022.. The individual performance indicators are ranked in descending order while the overall ranking is computed in ascending order. The overall financial performance of private sector banks is stronger than that of the public sector banks. HDFC Bank has the maximum return on equity followed by Kotak Mahindra Bank while Punjab National Bank has the least return on equity. Union Bank of India and Bank of Baroda have stronger capital adequacy than that of private sector banks. HDFC bank and Axis Bank possess good quality assets while the asset quality of Punjab National Bank is the weakest. Bank of Baroda possess maximum managerial efficiency while Kotak Mahindra Bank enjoys maximum earning as compared to other selected banks. Private sector banks enjoy greater liquidity than that of public sector banks. Kotak Mahindra Bank has major liquidity followed by HDFC Bank whereas Union Bank of India is ranked the lowest in terms of liquidity. HDFC Bank is ranked first in the overall financial performance followed by Axis Bank while Punjab National Bank is placed on the last rank.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
ROE	15	0.94	1.21	1.11	0.08	0.01
C	15	12.68	14.10	13.21	0.46	0.21
A	15	1.37	5.44	3.06	1.48	2.20
M	15	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.00
E	15	2.50	3.09	2.72	0.14	0.02
L	15	48.93	59.59	52.54	3.49	12.21

Source: All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

It is evident from the Table 2 that throughout the research period, the banks have registered a minimum ROE of 0.94% while the maximum reached to 1.21%. A mean result of 1.11% shows that most banks are doing well in their use of equity to produce profit for the investors. The average capital adequacy is 13.21%, which is more than the legal minimum of 9%. Asset quality of 3.06% is within the permitted range which indicates lower NPLs. The average earning capacity of the banks was 2.72%, which is a high return and shows that the management of the banks is wisely using the assets that are being used. The average liquidity level was 52.54%, indicating that the banks' lending operations are financed in part by the mobilised deposits.

Table 3. Pearson Coefficient of Correlation

Pearson Correlation	C	A	M	E	L
ROE	0.79	0.80	0.25	0.77	-0.73
Sig. (1-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.00

Source: All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Regression analysis makes the premise that there should not be any multicollinearity among the variables being studied. According to Nagaraju & Boateng (2018) a correlation coefficient between any two variables should not be greater than 0.80 to rule out the collinearity. Table 3 above shows that none of the correlation coefficients are more than 0.80 and thus, the variables under study are not multicollinear.

The Capital Adequacy was shown in the above table to have an unstandardized coefficient of 0.202 and a p value of 0.032. It implies that there is a strong correlation between the capital adequacy of selected banks and its performance.

Table 4. Multivariate Regression Analysis

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	
(Constant)	0.536	0.583	0.382
C	0.202	0.065*	0.032
A	0.309	0.025*	0.000
M	0.388	2.469	0.120
E	0.269	0.150*	0.000
L	-0.131	0.060	0.502
F- Statistics (Model Fit)	10.737		
D-W Statistics	1.836	R² = 0.985	

Source: All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Note: *Significant at 5 percent level

The ROE of the selected banks will improve by 20.2% for every unit increase in capital adequacy parameters.

Asset Quality showed a 0.309 coefficient with a 0.000 p value. It demonstrates that there is a link between asset quality and the performance of banks. The evidence suggests that a 1% reduction in non-performing assets will result in a 30.9% rise in the ROE of selected banks.

The unstandardized coefficient for management effectiveness was 0.388 with the p-value of 0.120. This indicates that, even a unit improvement in management effectiveness will result in 38.8% rise in ROE. However, it is not statistically significant.

Earning capacity had an unstandardized coefficient of 0.269 at a p value of 0.000. It showed a strong correlation between earnings and performance of the banks under study. It is evident from the data that with a unit increase in bank's earnings equate to a 26.9% increase in ROE.

With a p value of 0.502, the coefficient of liquidity was -0.131. This shows that there is a clear and inverse relationship between profitability and liquidity. It indicates that a unit drop in liquidity will cause a 13.1% increase in the ROE of the selected banks.

The table also provides the value of model summary (R²) wherein the independent variables predict the dependent variable (ROE) to a level of 98.5 percent based on the R-square value 0.985.

The D-W statistic value is 1.836 which clearly indicates that there is no auto-correlation detected in the sample.

7. Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Sig.	Remarks
H01: There is no significant relationship between Capital adequacy and ROE	0.032*	Rejected
H02: There is no significant relationship between Asset quality and ROE	0.000*	Rejected
H03: There is no significant relationship between Management efficiency and ROE	0.120	Accepted
H04: There is no significant relationship between Earning capacity and ROE	0.000*	Rejected
H05: There is no significant relationship between Liquidity and ROE	0.502	Accepted

Note: *Significant at 5 percent level

8. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of the study is to explore and assess the financial performance and credit risk management practices of the selected Indian commercial banks using the CAMEL model approach. The overall performance ranking of selected banks during the study period reveals that the HDFC Bank is ranked first in the overall financial performance followed by Axis Bank while Punjab National Bank sits on the last rank. It is evident from the data analysis that the capital adequacy, asset quality and earning capacity has a statistically significant effect on the performance (ROE) of the selected banks for the period under study. However, the relationship of management efficiency and liquidity with ROE is found to be statistically insignificant.

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